

THE PROBLEMS OF THE USAGE OF COMPLIMENTS IN THE COMMUNICATION PROCESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10430192>

Compliments have their own socially decisive significance as speech acts. They not only do well in terms of appreciating others, but they also reflect various ideals in various groups. People come from various backgrounds and live in various civilizations.

"Compliments are speech acts that are used to negotiate solidarity in daily conversation, which are related to the concepts of face work in politeness theory," in his thesis, Fujimaru used this term. In addition, he stated that compliments are formulaic since the words used in compliments are positive verbs and adjectives. Compliments, as Homes put it, are "social lubricants that develop or sustain rapport." As a result, they are mostly meant to have a positive impact.

Compliments have a simple function of praising others. "You did a fantastic job!" or "Way to go!" All of these words are encouraging, since they inspire individuals to be more confident in their abilities. Finally, it is usually used to bring a discourse to a close. "Nice to chat to you!" or "I am delighted to talk to you!" is a simple statement that conveys the speaker's emotions.

Compliments might be counterproductive.

There are benefits and drawbacks to everything. If the compliments, on the other hand, have a negative effect, they aren't the lubricants that are referred to as negative functions. The majority of the time, they are distinguished by the conversation's setting or atmosphere. If the compliments contain jealousy or any other unwelcome concept in the receivers' minds, they are not genuine sentiments from the speakers. Consider the following situation:

A juvenile error is made by one of our pals and we say, *"You are so adorable!"*

In this case, we may infer that giving praising meaning is impossible. As a result, it has the reverse connotation, implying that the speakers are laughing at the error or that they do not wish to criticize. In this scenario, compliments have a detrimental impact. The face of people will be threatened.

In a compliment, considered as a speech act, three main aspects should be distinguished: speech action, psychological interaction and a way of linguistic implementation of speech action.

The illocutionary goals of a compliment are to:

- to express the positive intentional state of the speaker, the representative content of which is an explicit or implicit positive value judgment;
- express the speaker's intention/aspiration/desire to please the addressee;
- Express a positive attitude of the speaker to the addressee.

The illocutionary act of a compliment is characterized by a wide range of expressed intentional states of the speaker - not only approval and admiration, but also respect, sympathy, love, affection, enjoyment, pleasure, etc.

The illocutionary act of a compliment is considered insincere when at least one of the expressed intentional states does not correspond to the actual one, and also when the positive value judgment that constitutes the propositional content does not correspond to the real assessment.

The perlocutionary purpose of a compliment is mainly to evoke a positive emotional reaction in the addressee, to give him pleasure. Perlocutionary acts of compliment can be not only intentional (deliberate), but also non-intentional. Non-intentional perlocutionary acts of compliment take place in situations where the positive reaction of the addressee, caused by the statement, was not part of the speaker's goals.

Humans can be split into two categories based on many factors. If individuals are classified as men or girls, it is based on biological sex, which is determined by their sex organs and DNA. When using gender to separate humans, on the other hand, individuals might use a psychological and cultural word that includes subjective experiences of maleness and femaleness. Gender, on the other hand, relates to how society views conduct as masculine or feminine.¹

There are still considerable distinctions in the social aspects of voice between men and women. Men, according to Spender, frequently utilize a lower pitched voice due of both their anatomy and their desire to do so.²

Men will be ridiculed if they use a high-pitched voice, and their image will suffer as a result. In men's perception, lower-pitched voices are more confident and dominant than higher-pitched voices. Men are frequently the most powerful group in society. They are the dominant and dominant group in society, whilst women are typically the subservient ones.

Gender is viewed by linguists as a grammatical concept that is closely related to speech and dialogues. In the early 1970s, research on how women and

¹ Basow, Susan A. (1992) Gender. 3rd edition. USA: Brooks/ Cole Publishing Company.

² Graddol, David & Swann, Joan. (1989) Gender Voices. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.

men communicate became a focal point of discourse and gender studies. There are four ways to studying gender and language, according to Lakoff: deficiency, dominance, difference, and social constructionist approaches. The last one, which deals with gender relations and emphasizes doing gender rather than being gender, is preferred by most linguists. That implies a female can play the role of a man if she wants to, and a male can play the role of a female if he wants to.

Some absolute disparities in speech actions between men and women have been discovered after extensive research:

- 1) Women are more socially engaged, cooperative, and constructive than men;
- 2) Women are more silent in public than men, making them a muted group;
- 3) Women ask more questions than men in speech patterns;
- 4) Women are interrupted more frequently than men;
- 5) Women have different lexical items choices and frequency than men;
- 6) Women use more politeness behaviors than men, such as compliments, apologies, minimal responses, and tag questions.

The majority of people give compliments to make you feel good. If you're like most people, though, those well-intentioned pleasant comments might be difficult to hear at times.

Here are four reasons why accepting a praise might be difficult:

1. You have a low sense of self-worth.

People with poor self-esteem had the most trouble taking praises, according to a recent study published in the Journal of Experimental Social Psychology. If you believe you have some flaws or that you aren't good enough, you may find it difficult to comprehend how others can say such nice things about you.

Compliments, according to the study, are unlikely to alter your unfavorable self-image. Worse, if the adulation comes from a love partner, those well-intentioned words of praise might end up hurting your relationship. You may believe your spouse is lying, leading to a loss of trust.³

2. Your Self-Image Is Disparate

Another reason compliments might make you feel uneasy is that the words you hear don't match how you view yourself. It's referred to as cognitive dissonance by psychologists, who use the term to characterize the discrepancies.

³ Journal of Experimental Social Psychology, Who can't take a compliment? The role of construal level and self-esteem in accepting positive feedback from close others. Volume 68, January 2017, Pages 40-49

Assume a colleague says, "You're a genius. In your reports, you always mention exactly the appropriate things."

Hearing those statements could throw you into a spiral if you don't think of yourself as a clever, capable person. You'll be left wondering if you're lacking in insight or if the other person is lacking in judgment. This is frequently the reason for people's justifications in response to compliments. Saying something like, "Well, I simply got fortunate this time," might help alleviate some of the anxiety that arises when someone's depiction of you differs from how you characterize yourself.

3. You're anxious about high expectations.

People with poor self-esteem like to set the bar low, according to studies. They are then pleasantly delighted if their expectations are met.

You'll feel a lot of pressure if you receive a compliment that indicates you're expected to do well. Those sweet words from your employer, "I chose you for this assignment since you usually make your deadlines," might be intimidating.

4. You Want to Be Humble

When someone says something like, "You're the best boss ever," or "You have amazing skill," it's difficult to know how to respond. "Yeah, I know," you'll undoubtedly come out as a jerk.

For many people, though, even a simple "Thank you" might be difficult. After all, boasting isn't a really appealing trait.

Humility has been related to a range of favorable outcomes, including enhanced self-control and successful leadership, according to studies. Accepting compliments, on the other hand, may sometimes feel more like a superiority complex than a polite acceptance.

Accepting compliments with difficulty might be a sign of a deeper issue. If you work on your self-esteem or your essential values, you could find that praises are easier to accept. Even if taking a compliment makes you feel embarrassed, you don't have to act awkwardly. The greatest way to respond to a compliment is to express thanks. Almost usually, a simple "thank you" is enough. Refrain from criticizing yourself, but acknowledge others who helped you achieve your goals.

References:

1. Basow, Susan A. (1992) Gender. 3rd edition. USA: Brooks/ Cole Publishing Company.
2. Graddol, David & Swann, Joan. (1989) Gender Voices. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.

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